

Biological Implications of Liquid Membrane Phenomena*

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Biological implications of the liquid membrane phenomena have been examined. Attention has been focussed on two aspects namely model system for biological membranes and mechanism of action of surface active drugs. Data have been obtained to indicate that the liquid membrane bilayers, generated on a hydrophobic supporting membrane from the constituents of biological membranes, are workable as model systems for biomembranes. It has also been observed that liquid membranes generated by surface active drugs play a significant role in the mechanism of their action. The two surface active drugs investigated are haloperidol and chlorpromazine.

ACCORDING to Kesting's hypothesis¹⁻³ which was originally propounded to account for enhanced salt rejection in reverse-osmosis due to addition of surfactants like polyvinyl methyl ether in the saline feed, a surface active substance when added to aqueous phase generates a surfactant layer liquid membrane at the interface. As concentration of the surfactant is increased the interface is progressively covered with the surfactant layer liquid membrane and at the critical micelle concentration (CMC) it is completely covered. Experimental validity of the hypothesis has been demonstrated by Srivastava and Yadav^{4,5}. In view of the fact that molecules of surface active nature are crucial to living matter and its organisation⁶, biological implications of the liquid membrane hypothesis are examined in the paper. The data obtained in recent studies^{7,8} from this laboratory have been utilised to indicate that the liquid membrane bilayers generated from the constituent lipids of biological membranes possess the potential of being used as model systems for biological membranes.

All drugs which act by modifying the permeability of cell membranes, of necessity, have to be surface active in nature. In fact a wide variety of drugs are known⁹ to be surface active and in many cases excellent correlations between surface activity and clinical potencies have been reported¹⁰. In the case of psychotropic drugs Palm *et al*¹¹ concluded that irrespective of chemical structures it is the surface activity that mainly determines their potencies towards all kinds of membranes especially that of catecholamine storing particles. Since surface active drugs, according to Kesting's hypothesis, can generate liquid membrane at the interface it is likely that the liquid membrane phenomena may have a role to play in the mechanism of action of such drugs. The data obtained in our recent experiments on two neuroleptic drugs namely haloperidol¹² and chlorpromazine¹³ are presented to highlight the role of liquid membranes generated by them in the mechanism of their action. This is the second objective of this paper. Since biological

effects of the drugs have, to date, been explained solely on the basis of specific and active interactions of the drugs with the constituents of biomembranes the present study draws attention towards an often overlooked, nevertheless, a new and important modality of the drug action.

Liquid membranes as model membrane systems :

Although black lipid membranes¹⁴ (BLMs) have been commonly used as model systems for biomembranes, certain facts about BLMs can not be ignored. The values of electrical resistance of BLMs are several order of magnitude higher¹⁵⁻¹⁷ than those of biomembranes¹⁸. Also, the rate of ionic diffusion through BLMs is much slower^{19,20} than through biomembranes^{21,22}. This is ascribed to a tight molecular arrangement²³ in BLMs while the lipid bilayer in biomembranes is in a fluid state²⁴. In this section are presented data from some of our recent studies^{7,8} which indicate that liquid membrane bilayers generated on a hydrophobic supporting membrane, using Kesting's hypothesis, can also act as a model system for biomembranes.

Hydraulic permeability data in presence of lecithin, cholesterol and lecithin-cholesterol mixtures and their analysis in light of mosaic membrane model²⁵⁻²⁷ has been utilised to demonstrate the formation of a liquid membrane generated by these substances at the interface. A Sartorius cellulose acetate microfiltration membrane (Cat. no. 11107)/aqueous interface has been used as site for the formation of liquid membrane in these experiments^{7,8}. Details of the experimental set up and the procedures used are available in the original papers^{7,8}. The Sartorius cellulose acetate microfiltration membrane which acted as a supporting membrane for the liquid membranes separated the transport cell in two compartments (C and D of Fig. 1 in ref. 7). It was demonstrated^{7,8} that when the two compartments of the transport cell are each filled with aqueous solutions of lipids -lecithin or cholesterol - of concentrations equal to or higher than their CMC, the supporting membrane is sand-

*Respectfully dedicated to the late Professor J. N. Mukherjee on the occasion of his 90th birthday.

wiched between the two layers of the liquid membranes generated by the lipids on either side of it. The CMC values of aqueous lecithin and aqueous cholesterol were found^{7,8} to be 1.599×10^{-5} and $30.08 \times 10^{-9} M$, respectively. In the case of lecithin-cholesterol mixtures it was shown⁹ that when the concentration of the lecithin-cholesterol mixture was $1.9188 \times 10^{-5} M$ with respect to lecithin (which is slightly higher than its CMC) and $1.175 \times 10^{-6} M$ with respect to cholesterol, the liquid membrane generated by lecithin is fully saturated with cholesterol. The concentration of lecithin was deliberately chosen slightly higher than its CMC to ensure complete coverage of the interface with the lecithin liquid membrane. The data on surface tension of lecithin-cholesterol mixtures when coupled with the data on hydraulic permeability in presence of lecithin-cholesterol mixtures revealed⁶ that cholesterol though penetrates the lecithin liquid membrane does not reach deep upto the interface and resides in cavities in the lecithin liquid membrane caused by thermal motions. This situation is analogous to the situation of cholesterol in the lipid bilayer of biomembranes^{2,3}. It was also shown that when the two compartments of the transport cell (Fig. 1 in ref. 7) are each filled with aqueous solutions of lecithin-cholesterol mixture of concentration $1.9188 \times 10^{-5} M$ with respect to lecithin and $1.175 \times 10^{-6} M$ with respect to cholesterol, the supporting membrane which separates the two compartments of the transport cell is sandwiched between the two layers of the liquid membrane generated by the lecithin-cholesterol mixtures on either side of it. In the liquid membrane bilayers thus generated by lecithin, cholesterol and their mixture it is logical to expect that the hydrophobic ends of the lipids would be preferentially oriented towards the hydrophobic supporting membrane and the hydrophilic ends drawn outwards away from it. Since, in these experiments, the liquid membranes are generated from aqueous solutions at the supporting membrane/aqueous solution interface they are expected to have more fluidity in them and hence in this respect are expected to be closer to the state of lipid bilayers in biomembranes. The transport data on the liquid membrane bilayers thus generated is therefore expected to be closer to the data on biomembranes. The values of electrical resistance for the liquid membrane bilayers generated by the lipids and their mixture, the values of cationic transport

number and permeabilities through the liquid membrane bilayers estimated from the data for the composite membrane consisting of supporting membrane sandwiched between the two layers of the lipid liquid membrane, and the data for the bare supporting membrane using Kedem and Katchalsky's theory for permeability of composite membranes^{20,21}, are given in Table 1. The details of the procedure and calculations are available in earlier publications^{7,8}. The agreement, though qualitative, of the transport data for the lecithin-cholesterol liquid membrane bilayers with those for

Fig. 1. The transport cell. The thick lines indicate the blackened portions. R—reflector; B—100 W bulb; F—optical filter; E₁ and E₂—platinum electrodes; M—the supporting membrane. The concentration of chloroplast extract used in photo-osmosis experiments was 46.4 ppm. The illuminated compartment contained Fe³⁺ ions ($1 \times 10^{-3} M$) and the dark compartment contained Fe³⁺ ions ($1 \times 10^{-8} M$).

TABLE 1—VALUES OF CATION PERMEABILITIES, NORMALIZED RESISTANCE AND CATIONIC TRANSPORT NUMBERS FOR VARIOUS LIQUID MEMBRANE BILAYERS

System	Permeability, $\text{cm s}^{-1} \times 10^6$					Resistance (R_m), $\Omega\text{-cm}^2$		Transport no. (t_i)			
	This work			Reported in lit.		This work	Reported in lit.	This work		Reported in lit.	
	Na ⁺	K ⁺	Ca ²⁺	Na ⁺	K ⁺			Na ⁺	K ⁺	Na ⁺	K ⁺
1. Lecithin bilayers	24.93	8.26	50.83	a	$3.4 \times 10^{-5}^b$	0.89×10^6	10^9^c	0.54	0.52	0.55^d	0.52^d
2. Cholesterol bilayers	31.03	15.88	57.58			0.51×10^6		0.57	0.56		
3. Lecithin-cholesterol bilayers	1.33	1.04	29.86	0.015^e	0.56^e	1.79×10^6	$10^8 - 10^9^g$	0.49	0.47		

^aUndetectable: for phosphatidylcholine BLM (ref 20). ^bFor phosphatidylcholine BLM (ref 19). ^cFor phosphatidylcholine BLM (ref 17). ^dFor phosphatidylcholine (egg) (ref 50). ^eFor squid axon (resting) (ref 21). ^fFor frog sartorius muscle (resting) (ref 22). For biomembranes (ref 18).

the living membranes/BLMs is encouraging and indicates the possibility of using the liquid membrane bilayers thus generated as model systems for bio-membranes.

Photo-osmosis :

To assess the workability of this possibility it is desirable to simulate some of the biologically relevant transport processes on such liquid membrane bilayers. Light induced transport processes through thylakoid membrane of the chloroplast afford a situation where such a simulation can be attempted. Gradients of light across chloroplast BLMs have been shown³⁰ to induce volume flux. The light induced volume flux which can be termed as photoosmosis is considered to be a consequence of electrical potentials developed across the BLMs due to action of light, the photoelectric effect³⁰. Chloroplast extract is known to be surface active in nature³¹ and hence according to Kesting's hypothesis can generate liquid membrane which would completely cover the interface at a concentration equal to or greater than its CMC. Therefore it should be possible using the procedure adopted^{7,8} in the case of lecithin, cholesterol and their mixture to generate liquid membranes from chloroplast extract on either side of a hydrophobic supporting membrane. The chloroplast liquid membrane bilayers thus generated should also show the phenomenon of photo-osmosis. In a recent study from this laboratory³² it has been demonstrated that the chloroplast liquid membrane bilayers thus generated do show the phenomenon of photo-osmosis. A summary of these investigations³² is given below.

The transport cell used for photo-osmosis studies is depicted in Fig. 1. A Sartorius cellulose acetate membrane (Cat. no 11107) which acts as support for the liquid membrane divides the cell in two compartments. As in the case of lecithin, cholesterol and their mixture, the hydraulic permeability data was exploited in this case also to demonstrate the existence of a liquid membrane generated by chloroplast extract. Chloroplast extract for these studies were obtained from spinach leaves using the method described in literature³³. The CMC of aqueous solution of chloroplast extract was found to be 23.184 ppm. For photo-osmosis experiments the two halves of the transport cell (Fig. 1) separated by the supporting membrane were each filled with an aqueous solution of the chloroplast extract of concentration higher than its CMC (46.4 ppm). The concentration higher than the CMC was chosen to make sure that the liquid membranes generated by chloroplast completely cover the supporting membrane on either side. Needless to mention, in the chloroplast liquid membranes the hydrophobic ends will be preferentially oriented towards the hydrophobic supporting membrane. The compartment C (Fig. 1) which was exposed to light contained desired concentration of Fe^{3+} ions, an electron acceptor and the compartment D (Fig. 1) which was kept dark contained desired concentration of Fe^{2+} ions, an

electron donor. To begin with the experiment the condition of no net pressure difference $\Delta P=0$ was imposed on the system. The light was then switched on and the consequent movement of the liquid meniscus in the capillary L_1L_2 was noted. During the measurements of photo-osmotic velocity a constant and stabilised voltage at 220 volts from A.C. mains was fed to the bulb B and the distance between the transport cell and the bulb was kept fixed. In order to study the variation of photo-osmotic velocity with intensity of exciting light, various voltages were fed to the bulb to alter the intensity of the exciting light. All experiments were carried out at constant temperature of $40 \pm 1^\circ$ using a thermostat.

A general observation in these experiments was that the direction of photo-osmotic volume flux was always from the lighted compartment to the dark compartment. This calls for an explanation. Tien's observations on light induced water flow across chloroplast-BLMs were explained^{30,34,35} in terms of semiconductor physics and classical electrokinetics. When a beam of light excites the BLM, electrons and holes are produced. Since electrons and holes have different life times and mobilities, a separation of charges in the BLM results leading eventually to a potential difference across the membrane. The light induced voltage across the BLM was considered to be the primary driving force for photo-osmosis. Similar explanation can be extended in the present case also to account for the origin of the effect and direction of the flow. The chloroplast liquid membrane on excitation by light ejects electrons which are captured by the electron acceptor Fe^{3+} ions present in the illuminated compartment. Upon reduction of Fe^{3+} ions by photo electrons or hydrated electrons an electrical double layer is generated which consists of a layer of anions in the solution—the mobile phase of the double layer and a layer of positively charged oxidised chloroplast in the membrane phase. Since the illuminated compartment where electrons are generated due to the action of light is negative with respect to the dark compartment, the negatively charged mobile phase of the double layer moves from the illuminated compartment to the dark compartment.

Although the present experiments were carried out under constant temperature conditions, the possibility of the thermal gradients, produced by light absorption, causing the observed flow has to be ruled out. The observations, in the present experiments, that movement of the liquid in the capillary L_1L_2 was noticed instantaneously as soon as the light was switched on and also that the flow stopped instantaneously as soon as light was switched off, strongly suggest that the observed volume flux can not be the result of thermal gradients because establishment and abolition of thermal gradients can not be an instantaneous process. It was also observed that on short-circuiting the electrodes E_1 and E_2 the light induced volume flux stopped completely. This observation not only rules out the possibility of thermal

gradients being a cause for the observed flow but also confirms that the light induced voltage across the membrane is the primary cause for the observed photo-osmosis as suggested by Tien in the case of chloroplast-BLMs¹⁰.

If light generated electrons and their capture by the electron acceptors present in the illuminated compartment are responsible for the observed photo-osmotic effect, the values of photo-osmotic velocity should increase with the increasing concentrations of electron acceptors. The data on photo-osmotic velocity at various concentrations of Fe²⁺ ions in the illuminated compartment keeping the concentration of Fe²⁺ ions in the dark compartment constant (1 × 10⁻³ M) confirms such a trend (Table 2).

TABLE 2—VALUES OF PHOTO-OSMOTIC VELOCITY AT VARIOUS CONCENTRATIONS OF ELECTRON ACCEPTOR (Fe²⁺ IONS) IN THE ILLUMINATED COMPARTMENT

Solution in the cell	Concentration of Fe ²⁺ ions in the illuminated compartment	Photo-osmotic velocity × 10 ⁵ (m sec ⁻¹)
Chloroplast extract	1 × 10 ⁻⁴ M	0.096 ± 0.020
	5 × 10 ⁻⁴ M	0.186 ± 0.056
	1 × 10 ⁻³ M	0.358 ± 0.027
	5 × 10 ⁻³ M	0.598 ± 0.041
	1 × 10 ⁻² M	0.756 ± 0.013

The dark compartment in all cases contained Fe²⁺ ions at 1 × 10⁻³ M.

The open circuit photo-voltages (E_{o.p.}) in the case of chloroplast-BLMs are known to be dependent on the intensity of exciting light (I). The dependence has been found to be given by the following equation¹⁴

$$E_{o.p.} = l \log \left(1 + \frac{I}{L} \right) \quad \dots (1)$$

where l and L are constants for a given chloroplast-BLM at a particular temperature. Under conditions of low light intensities, E_{o.p.} becomes directly proportional to I as has indeed been found to be the case. As an implication of this it follows that the photo-osmotic velocity through the liquid membrane bilayers should also show a similar dependence on the intensity of exciting light. The results (Fig. 2) indeed show such a dependence on the intensity of exciting light.

Fig. 2. Variation of photo-osmotic velocity with intensity of light. The intensity was varied by feeding different voltages to the light source.

The values of photo-osmotic velocity induced by light of different wavelengths obtained using different optical filters are recorded in Table 3. In the system containing chloroplast extract chlorophylls are the main photo active materials whose major absorption peaks¹⁵ are at 400 and 660 nm. The peak at 400 nm is more intense than the peak at 660 nm. The magnitude of photo-osmotic velocity at various wavelength ranges shows the same gradation indicating that the photo-osmotic flow is due to absorption of light by the pigments.

Liquid membranes in drug action :

In this section we present the data obtained recently^{12,13} in our laboratory on two neuroleptic drugs namely haloperidol and chlorpromazine to highlight the role of liquid membranes generated by them in the mechanism of their action. Both haloperidol and chlorpromazine were found to be surface active with their CMCs, as determined from the variation of surface tension with concentration, equal to 1.064 × 10⁻⁶ and 4.5 × 10⁻⁸ M, respectively. In these experiments a Sartorius microfiltration membrane—a cellulose acetate or a cellulose nitrate membrane/aqueous interface was

TABLE 3—VALUES OF THE PHOTO-OSMOTIC VELOCITY AT DIFFERENT WAVELENGTH RANGES

	Wavelength (nm)				
	White light	365-445 (Filter no. N-Hg-2)*	465-565 (Filter no. B-505)*	560-660 (Filter no. B-610)*	600-660 (Filter no. N-630)*
Chloroplast Extract					
Photo-osmotic velocity × 10 ⁵ (m sec ⁻¹)	3.580 ± 0.027	2.382 ± 0.003	1.315 ± 0.001	1.599 ± 0.001	2.031 ± 0.002

* Obtained from Photovolt Corporation, New York. The dark compartment contained Fe²⁺ ions (1 × 10⁻³ M) and the illuminated compartment contained Fe²⁺ ions (1 × 10⁻³ M).

chosen as site for the formation of liquid membranes so that the specific interaction of the drug with the components of biological membranes is totally ruled out and data on passive transport alone is obtained. Evidence in favour of liquid membrane formation was obtained from the hydraulic permeability data in presence of the drugs. The experimental set up and the procedures used are described in the original papers^{12,13}. For measurement of solute permeability (ω) of the relevant permeants in presence of the liquid membrane generated by the drugs, two sets of experiments were performed. In the first set, the compartment C of the transport cell (Fig. 1 in ref. 12) was filled with an aqueous solution containing known concentration of the drug and the permeant and the compartment D was filled with water. In the second set, the compartment D was filled with an aqueous solution of the drug of the same concentration as in the first set and the compartment C was filled with an aqueous solution of known concentration of the permeant. In the control experiments, however, no drug was used. Since according to Kesting's hypothesis the interface is completely covered with the liquid membrane generated by the surface active substance when its concentration equals or exceeds the critical micelle concentration the concentrations of the drugs used in the solute permeability experiments were higher than their CMCs—the concentrations of haloperidol and chlorpromazine were 4.256×10^{-6} and 1.8×10^{-4} M, respectively—so that the supporting membrane of the transport cell (Fig 1, in ref. 12) is completely covered with the drug liquid membrane. The details of the solute permeability (ω) experiments are given in the original papers^{12,13}.

Since both haloperidol and chlorpromazine are surface active in nature, they have both hydrophobic and hydrophilic groups in their structure. In the first set of experiments, therefore, the liquid membrane generated by the drugs would present a hydrophilic surface to the approaching permeants because the hydrophobic ends of the drug molecules will be preferentially oriented towards the hydrophobic supporting membrane. In the second set of experiments, however, the permeants present in the compartment C would face the hydrophobic surface of the liquid membrane generated by the drug present in the compartment D.

The data on solute permeability (ω) in the case of both haloperidol and chlorpromazine are recorded in Tables 4 and 5. The data indicate that the transport of endogenous amines and amino acids is impeded most when the approaching permeants face the hydrophobic surface of the liquid membrane (the second set experiments). Since both haloperidol and chlorpromazine are known²⁷⁻²⁹ to act by reducing the permeability of endogenous amines and amino acids, it appears that the specific orientation of the drugs with hydrophobic ends of the molecules facing the permeants may be necessary even in biological cells. This implies that the receptor should have hydrophilic moieties projected outwards to which the

hydrophilic ends of the drugs get attached. Such an orientation can be rationalised if one examines the nature of the receptors, in general, in relation to the lipid bilayer part of the biomembranes.

TABLE 4—SOLUTE PERMEABILITY ω OF ENDOGENOUS AMINES, AMINO ACIDS AND CATIONS IN PRESENCE OF 4.256×10^{-6} M HALOPERIDOL

	$\omega_1 \times 10^{12}$ moles/s N	$\omega_2 \times 10^{12}$ moles/s N	$\omega_3 \times 10^{12}$ moles/s N	$\omega_4 \times 10^{12}$ moles/s N
Dopamine	887.3	680.0	2607.0	274.4
Noradrenaline	75.8	65.9	294.3	
Adrenaline	50.7	undetectable	237.4	
Serotonin	193.7	94.5	348.1	
Glutamic acid	58.9	47.3	81.0	
γ -Aminobutyric acid	119.8	86.6	152.2	

ω_1 : control value—without haloperidol.

ω_2 : haloperidol in compartment D of the transport cell.

ω_3 : haloperidol in compartment C of the transport cell.

ω_4 : in the presence of γ -aminobutyric acid and haloperidol.

TABLE 5—SOLUTE PERMEABILITY ω OF BIOGENIC AMINES AND AMINO ACIDS IN PRESENCE OF 1.8×10^{-4} M CHLORPROMAZINE HYDROCHLORIDE

	$\omega_1 \times 10^{12}$ moles/s N	$\omega_2 \times 10^{12}$ moles/s N	$\omega_3 \times 10^{12}$ moles/s N	$\omega_4 \times 10^{12}$ moles/s N
Dopamine	1015.0	344.9	531.5	70.98
Noradrenaline	778.7	166.3	609.0	
Adrenaline	2535.0	301.5	2000.0	
Serotonin	842.8	164.1	334.2	
Glutamic acid	426.0	325.1	366.0	
γ -Aminobutyric acid	784.7	608.3	624.1	

ω_1 : Control value—without chlorpromazine.

ω_2 : Chlorpromazine in compartment D of the transport cell and permeant in compartment C.

ω_3 : Chlorpromazine in compartment C of the transport cell and permeant in compartment C.

ω_4 : Chlorpromazine and γ -aminobutyric acid in compartment D and permeants in compartment C.

The receptors, in general, are membrane proteins and hence have to be surface active in nature. Thus they will have both hydrophilic and hydrophobic moieties in their structure. Since the exterior environment of biological cells is aqueous in nature, it is logical to expect that hydrophobic part of these membrane proteins will be associated with hydrophobic core of the lipid bilayers and only hydrophilic part will face the exterior. Thus hydrophilic part of the drugs will preferably interact with the hydrophilic part of the receptor protein, leaving out the hydrophobic part to face the permeant. Prediction about similar orientation of receptor proteins in general has been made recently⁴⁰.

Although the resistance offered by the drug liquid membranes to the permeants is passive in nature it is likely to be accompanied by reduction in their active transport as well. This is because the liquid membrane generated by the drug is likely to reduce the access of the permeants to the active site located on the biomembrane.

The data in Tables 4 and 5 also show that the liquid membranes generated by both haloperidol and chlorpromazine impede the transport of γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA) and glutamic acid. The major factor for the antipsychotic action of both haloperidol and chlorpromazine is the reduction in permeability to dopamine^{37,41} which is under the influence of GABA-glutamic acid system³⁷. To investigate whether similar trend is observed on a non-specific membrane like the one chosen in these experiments, permeability of dopamine was measured in presence of GABA. It is interesting to note that the addition of GABA further reduces the permeability of dopamine through the drug liquid membranes (Tables 4 and 5). This appears to be due to the strengthening of the hydrophobic core of the liquid membranes generated by the drugs - haloperidol or chlorpromazine, by GABA. This is evident from the structural similarity of the hydrophobic components of their structures given below :

It is reported⁴² that haloperidol is considerably more potent on a milligram basis than chlorpromazine *in vivo*. The liquid membrane phenomena might explain this. Because haloperidol is more surface active^{12,18} than chlorpromazine, as is obvious from their CMC values, the former will form liquid membranes at a lower concentration, making it pharmacologically effective even at a comparatively lower concentration.

A perusal of Table 4 reveals that haloperidol reduces the permeability of serotonin. This is in agreement with the observations reported on biological cells⁴³. The extrapyramidal effects of antipsychotic drugs are reported to be resistant to levodopa therapy⁴⁴. Since reduced concentration of serotonin in cerebrospinal fluid has also been linked with a defect of extrapyramidal function^{45,46}, the reduced permeability of serotonin in presence of antipsychotic drugs like haloperidol and chlorpromazine offers a clue to the causation of extrapyramidal symptoms.

Thus, modification in the permeabilities of relevant permeants due to the formation of liquid membranes at the interface seems to have notable contribution to the mechanism of their action. Since the two drugs discussed in this section are structurally dissimilar, the role of surface activity of the drugs through the liquid membranes generated by them is conspicuous in the mechanism of their action. Recent studies from our group on reserpine⁴⁷, imipramine⁴⁸ and diazepam⁴⁹ have further confirmed the role of liquid membrane phenomena in the mechanism of action of surface active drugs.

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